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MYSTIC AND ESOTERIC MOVEMENTS IN THEORY AND PRACTICE

Fifth International Conference

HISTORY AND DISCOURSE
Historical and Philosophical Aspects of the
Study of Esotericism and Mysticism

Association for the Study of Esotericism and Mysticism

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WESTERN ESOTERICISM: THE NEXT GENERATION

In this article I would like to present some reflections on the current state of the study of «Western esotericism» and make some recommendations for the future development of the field. My title intends, firstly, to make a playful allusion to the second installment of a famous science fiction series, «Star Trek», in which captain Jean-Luc Picard and his crew take over from the team of captain Kirk. The famous motto of «Star Trek: The Next Generation», «to boldly go where no one has gone before» is quite appropriate to our field of study, for it is true that we are trying to give scholarly attention to topics and traditions that have often been wholly neglected and ignored by previous generations, and treated as if they did not exist. The theme of bold exploration of the unknown is therefore certainly fitting to describe our work. But more seriously, my title also means to allude to the theme of technical and conceptual innovation and progress. In the development of computer software, we see regular upgrades from one «generation» to the next. I will be arguing that in the study of our field, we have now seen two generations, «Western Esotericism 1.0» and «Western Esotericism 2.0», and it is time for an upgrade to the next generation: «Western Esotericism 3.0».

In 2012, we have cause to celebrate the 20-year anniversary of «Western Esotericism 2.0», which (as I will argue) was released in 1992. I have been so fortunate as to be involved in the development of that «package» or «program» from the beginning, so let me begin by going back into history a bit, to summarize the main lines of development.

Western Esotericism 1.0

I will begin with a personal memory. In 1992, the Italian Center for the Study of New Religious Movements, CESNUR, organized a large conference on magic in Lyon, France [Martin, Laplantine 1994], and many of the most important scholars of esotericism happened to be present at the occasion. I had just started working on my Ph. D. research, and this was one of my very first academic conferences. Here in Lyon, I was thrilled to meet a whole range of scholars involved in the study of esotericism, some of whom I knew already from their work, and some of whom I had never heard of before: they included such names as Joscelyn Godwin, Massimo Introvigne, Hans Thomas Hakl, Jean-Pierre Laurant,

and, most of all, Antoine Faivre. I will never forget the circumstances (in a restaurant during lunch-time) under which I made the acquaintance of Faivre, the undisputed master scholar of Western esotericism at the time, who would become a very good friend and with whom I would come to collaborate very closely and productively during the years and decades to follow. In this year, 1992, Faivre had just published a short Introduction to the study of Western esotericism, in a famous French pocketbook series known as «Que sais-je?» [Faivre 1992], and with hindsight, this small volume must be seen as marking the end of the first and the beginning of the second cycle of Western Esotericism as a field of academic research: or in other words, it marked the transition from «Western Esotericism 1.0» to «Western Esotericism 2.0».

So what had «Western Esotericism 1.0» been all about? It is well known that an academic chair devoted to «History of Christian Esotericism» was created at the École Pratique des Hautes Études (Sorbonne) as early as 1964. But it is less well known that this occurred almost by chance, and certainly not as part of any deliberate effort to establish a new field of study¹. What happened is that the great scholar Alexandre Koyré (known from his standard works on Jacob Böhme and on the Copernican revolution [Koyré 1929; 1957]) had died, and his chair thus became vacant. The board of the EPHE saw François Secret, a well-known historian of Christian kabbalah, as a suitable candidate for succession; but in order to appoint him, the title of the chair had to be changed so as to make it fit Secret's field of specialization. One of the members of the board, the famous specialist of Islamic mysticism Henry Corbin, proposed to re-label the chair as «History of Christian Esotericism». The proposal came at the end of a long and exhausting faculty meeting, everybody was tired and wanted to go home, and so Corbin's colleagues said «well, OK, why not?». When Secret was appointed the next year, he was not exactly happy: the term «esotericism» embarrassed him, and he never made an effort to develop the field as an academic area of specialization. Therefore it would hardly be correct to say that the study of Western esotericism was already established as a field of study during the 1960s. After Secret's retirement in 1979, the title was modified into «History of Esoteric and Mystical Currents in Modern and Contemporary Europe», leading to a competition between the specialist of mysticism Michel de Certeau and Antoine Faivre, whose name was associated rather with «esotericism». Faivre was elected, and began to conceptualize the field as an academic specialty during the 1980s.

¹ For what follows, see [Faivre 2009: 123–124; Hanegraaff 2012: 348–349].

Now, in order to understand what «esotericism» meant at that time, one must take two factors into account. The first factor was the impact, in French scholarship, of a book published in 1928: Auguste Viatte's «*Les sources occultes du Romantisme*» («*The Occult Sources of Romanticism*») [Viatte 1928]. This book is and remains a classic. Based on extensive archival research, Viatte had demonstrated that the eighteenth century, the so-called «Age of Enlightenment», had been an age of mystical or esoteric «illuminism» as well. That an entire illuminist (sub)culture had flourished in France and Germany in the decades before the French Revolution (not only next to the rationalist current, but interwoven with it in many respects) came as a sensation to the scholarly world [Eliade 1973: 89]. The result was a «boom» of illuminist studies in French scholarship. The young Antoine Faivre was wholly representative of that phenomenon, with his important dissertations on Eckartshausen and Kirchberger published during the 1960s [Faivre 1966; 1969]. He would probably have spent the rest of his career as a specialized historian in Germanic studies, focused on illuminism, had it not been for a second main factor: the impact on his thinking of what is known as the Eranos approach to religion. It is essentially due to this second factor that Faivre became the scholar of «Western esotericism» that we know today. So what was Eranos all about?

Eranos was the name of an annual summer conference organized in Ascona, Switzerland, since 1933¹. Before the Second World War, the dominating figure at these conferences was the psychologist Carl Gustav Jung; but after the war, they were dominated by a whole range of famous, top-level specialists in the study of mythology and religion, including such names as Gershom Scholem, Henry Corbin, and Mircea Eliade. Against the dominant tendencies of secularization and disenchantment, Eranos highlighted the importance of myth and symbolism as vital dimensions of human culture, and gave much attention to «non-rational» factors in the history of the Western religious traditions. As I have argued at length elsewhere, the heart and core of the Eranos approach was a perspective on the study of religion that is technically known as «religionism» [Hanegraaff 2012: 126–127, 149, 276–277, 295–296, 311–312]. Religionism can be defined as a program of «exploring historical sources in search of what is eternal and universal». This is a deeply paradoxical project, for it essentially means that in studying history and change, one is looking for whatever transcends history and does not

¹ Generally on Eranos, see [Hakl 2001; Wasserstrom 1999; Hanegraaff 2012: 277–314]. On Faivre's development, including his involvement in Eranos, see [Hanegraaff 2012: 334–355].

change. The deep concern of Eranos religionism was with overcoming «the terror of history» and finding access to abiding truths of «the sacred» that could not be touched by transiency and time.

Antoine Faivre participated in Eranos during the later 1960s and the first half of the 1970s, and its religionist vision had a very deep impact on his thinking. Together with Henry Corbin and a small group of like-minded scholars and intellectuals, he stood at the origin of a radical French offshoot of the Eranos vision: a para-academic venture, in the form of an annual conference, known as the «Université Saint Jean de Jérusalem» («the University of St. John of Jerusalem») [Ibid.: 341–343]. There is no doubt that the group of intellectuals involved in this «Université» were preoccupied with much more than just scholarly research. In the words of its founder, Henry Corbin, they were deeply concerned with defending «the unique sovereignty of the spirit» against «the total confusion in the spirits, souls, and hearts, a confusion resulting from the disaster of the secular institutions of the West» [Corbin 1975: 8-9]. Corbin, Gilbert Durand, Faivre, and their collaborators were explicit in presenting «esotericism» as the «inner» dimension of true spirituality, and of their «Université Saint Jean de Jérusalem» as a visible manifestation of the «Inner Church» of the Spirit. This was their way of speaking about the universal, «sacred» dimension that was so important in the Eranos context. These strong spiritual commitments were carried by a deep personal involvement in contemporary esoteric rites and organizations within a Masonic context. Faivre, Corbin, and their friends and colleagues were all initiates in the so-called «Rectified Scottish Rite», a Christian chivalric system created by Jean-Baptiste Willermoz in 1778, and its «inner order», the «Chevaliers Bienfaisants de la Cité Sainte» (Benevolent Knights of the Holy City) [Hanegraaff 2012: 340–341]. In short, they were not only scholars but practicing esotericists as well.

When Faivre was elected to the chair for «Esoteric and Mystical Currents in Modern and Contemporary Europe» in 1979, he originally understood it entirely along these religionist lines inspired by Eranos and the «Université Saint Jean de Jérusalem»: while working as a specialized scholar of eighteenth and early nineteenth century theosophy and illuminism, he was also known as an explicit advocate of «esotericism» understood as an «inner» dimension of true spirituality that should be recovered by modern man. The religionist understanding of «esotericism» was still clearly evident in his major publications of the 1980s, notably his «Accès de l'ésotérisme occidental» of 1986 (later also translated into English). But Faivre's perspective began to change during the 1980s, largely as a result of academic internationalization [Hanegraaff 2012:

351–352]. He spent long periods as a visiting professor at the University of Berkeley; he got involved in international conferences on topics such as hermeticism and alchemy, dominated by strict historians with little or no interest in religionist agendas; and he became a regular attendant of the annual meetings of the American Academy of Religion (the A.A.R.). Faivre's vision became larger and broader; he developed a new interest in the esoteric «new religious movements» of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries; and perhaps most importantly, his growing irritation about the dogmatic anti-modernism and intolerant attitudes of the «perennialists» (or «traditionalists») at the A.A.R. seems to have caused a new appreciation, on his part, for the virtues of academic neutrality and secular historiography that had always been prominent in his own home institution, the Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes.

Western Esotericism 2.0

As a result of these various developments, Faivre moved away, during the later 1980s, from a religionist agenda towards a more deliberately historical and «neutral» approach; and this is what one sees in his small textbook «L'ésotérisme» of 1992, which marks the end of Faivre's religionist period. In sum: «Western esotericism 1.0» stands for the early religionist phase, largely dominated by one single scholar: Faivre himself. The second phase, «Western esotericism 2.0», began in 1992. Next to his French textbook, in this same year Faivre also co-edited a large collective volume in English, with Jacob Needleman [Modern Esoteric Spirituality 1992]. Both publications highlighted his famous definition of Western esotericism as a «form of thought» consisting of four intrinsic characteristics: correspondences, living nature, imagination / mediations, transmutation [Faivre 1992: 14–21; Modern Esoteric Spirituality 1992: xv–xx]. The same elements would be repeated in a series of further publications and translations in English during the following years. And finally, the year 1992 was also the beginning of increasingly intense collaboration with an international network of scholars interested in esotericism. Landmark events in that regard were the conferences of the International Association for the History of Religion (I.A.H.R.): they began to accept sessions on esotericism for the first time in 1995 [Western Esotericism and the Science of Religion 1998], and continued doing so in all their later conferences (Durban 2000; Tokyo 2005; Toronto 2010).

That the academy began to accept Western esotericism as a legitimate field of study was essentially due to two factors. First, Faivre's definition proved to be a very handy tool for defining and demarcating what the

field was all about. And second, «Western esotericism 2.0» was making a deliberate turn away from religionist agendas and towards an «empirical» and strictly historical approach. This «empirical turn» was essential, because it convinced the wider academic community that the study of esotericism was a legitimate scholarly pursuit like any other, and not a vehicle for hidden esoteric agendas. The combination of historical empiricism and an easily applicable definition resulted in what could be called the «Faivre paradigm» in the study of esotericism.

There is no need here to go into the details of the further development of «Western esotericism» as an academic pursuit¹. Important landmarks were the creation in 1999 of a second academic chair plus a complete teaching program at the University of Amsterdam, with which I had the honour of being entrusted; the creation in 2001 of a peer-review journal «Aries», published by Brill, followed by a closely related monograph series known as the «Aries Book Series»; the publication in 2005 of the «Dictionary of Gnosis and Western Esotericism» [Dictionary 2005], the creation, in the same year, of a third chair and teaching program at the University of Exeter; and the creation, still in 2005, of the European Society for the Study of Western Esotericism (E.S.S.W.E.)², which has already organized three biannual conferences, in Tübingen (Germany)³, Strasbourg (France), and Szeged (Hungary). The next conference will take place in Gothenburg (Sweden) in 2013. All these initiatives have created much excitement among a new generation of scholars, so that the study of Western esotericism has become an increasingly normal part of the study of religion. It is illustrative of this fact that the American Academy of Religion (A.A.R.) has given the field a protected status in recent years, and successful sessions are now organized there every year. It is particularly gratifying to see how many young and upcoming scholars are committing themselves to the study of Western esotericism, for they will be carrying the field further when the «founders» will have left the scene. Last but not least, next to the E.S.S.W.E. and its American counterpart, the Association for the Study of Esotericism (A.S.E.), we have seen the emergence of regional or national organizations devoted to the field, for example in Scandinavia (S.N.A.W.E.), Israel (I.N.A.S.W.E.), and of course the A.S.E.M. here in Russia. There is every reason to expect that this development will continue further into the future.

¹ For an overview of the earlier period, see [Hanegraaff 2004]. See also [Hermes in the Academy 2009; Hanegraaff 2012: 355–361].

² See the website: www.esswe.org.

³ See the volume based on the proceedings: [Kilcher 2010].

All of this may sound like a success story, and in many ways it is. In 1992 there existed no more than a very small and local religionist program, carried more or less by one single scholar: «Western Esotericism 1.0». Over the last twenty years, it has been upgraded to a very lively and dynamic international field of academic activity, «Western esotericism 2.0», and there is every reason to expect that it will keep developing and expanding. However, although much has been accomplished, it would be a mistake to think that the goal has been attained. If one makes a systematic survey of existing Textbooks and Introductions to Western esotericism, one sees that we still have a long way to go before the field will have reached full maturity. Faivre's small textbook of 1992 was unique at the time; but today one can choose between a whole range of Introductory books, by authors such as Kocku von Stuckrad [Stuckrad 2005], Arthur Versluis [Versluis 2007], or Nicholas Goodrick-Clarke [Goodrick-Clarke 2008]. Furthermore, Faivre has kept updating his Introduction as well [Faivre 2010]. If one goes through all of them, one begins to discover patterns that are a cause for concern [Hanegraaff 2013]. «Western esotericism 2.0» is a much better program than its predecessor, but in my opinion it still contains a number of bugs and design faults: in order to compete successfully on the developing market it will need to be upgraded. So what are the main problems?

1) A very important concern is the strong and continuing influence of outdated paradigms. I am thinking here particularly of the perspectives from the so-called Warburg School, with major scholars such as Frances A. Yates and D. P. Walker. Walker was a very important pioneer, with his groundbreaking studies of «Spiritual and Demonic Magic from Ficino to Campanella» [Walker 1958] and «The Ancient Theology» [Walker 1972]; and Frances Yates became an academic celebrity with her «Giordano Bruno and the Hermetic Tradition» [Yates 1964] and a range of further studies on Rosicrucianism, the Occult Philosophy of the Elizabethan Age, and so on. The study of Western esotericism owes a lot to these pioneers and we have reason to be grateful for their contributions, but we also have to face up to the fact that their works are now about half a century old, and many of their original insights have been superseded by more recent research. For example, Frances Yates' concept of a grand «Hermetic Tradition» in the early modern period is impossible to uphold: it is true that there was much interest for the Hermetic writings during the Renaissance, but this interest was part of a much larger revival that might be called «Platonic Orientalism» [Hanegraaff 2012: 12–17], in which other ancient authors such as Zoroaster were as important as Hermes. Most of Yates' figureheads (Ficino, Pico, Bruno, and so on) cannot in fact

be described as «hermeticists», and most of the real «hermeticists», such as Lodovico Lazzarelli, were marginalized in her narrative. Also, it is incorrect to assume, as Frances Yates did, that Hermeticism was a predominantly «magical» tradition; and this has far-reaching consequences because it undermines her idea that the scientific revolution had its origins in the «hermetic revival». On many matters of detail, I could go on listing the problems of the «Yates paradigm», but these points should suffice for now¹. The problem is that when it comes to the history of esotericism in the Renaissance, most scholars today are still falling back on the famous books by Yates, Walker, and related authors influenced by the Warburg school. They thereby keep adopting ideas about a massive, semi-autonomous “esoteric tradition” that I believe is simply no longer tenable on the basis of current research.

2) A second problem is that too many scholars seem to be either incapable or unwilling to make a clear distinction between *personal and scholarly engagement*. In itself it is obviously no problem if, next to their research, a scholar has some kind of personal investment in certain forms of esotericism. But it is essential to keep the two clearly apart: one cannot and should not try to wear the esoteric and the scholarly hat simultaneously. Far too often, however, one sees that scholarly analyses are influenced by personal esoteric agendas. It is abundantly clear that, in many cases, scholars are simply happy that, due to the emergence of «Western esotericism» as a field of study, they now finally have a chance to talk about their favorite topics in an academic setting. But too few scholars, in my opinion, have yet recognized the fact that esotericism has an enormous, even revolutionary *scholarly* potential for improving, revising, even overthrowing mainstream academic narratives about the history of religion and culture in the West. In other words: instead of grasping the chance of causing a revolution in mainstream academic research (as Frances Yates did during the 1960), scholars in esotericism too often seem to be concerned merely by pursuing their own personal and esoteric hobbies.

3) A third problem is the continuing influence of *religionism* in the study of esotericism. This point is linked to the previous one, but does not coincide with it. As I tried to explain above, religionism is essentially an attempt to speak about absolute, universal, unchanging spiritual truth within the framework of historical research. The problem is that this leads inevitably to an obsession with continuity and universality at the expense of historical diversity, innovation, and change. In other words, religionist scholars tend to overemphasize the similarities that they see between

¹ For a discussion of all these points, see [Hanegraaff 2012: 322–334].

different esoteric currents in different historical periods, and underestimate the differences. As a result, they tend to be much less interested in such things as historical *discontinuities*, creative innovation, new ideas and new departures, diversity, and sheer detail. They tend to look mostly at «the great lines of continuity», and this goes at the expense of looking at the specificity and uniqueness of historical currents or personalities. As a result, they tend to miss much of what makes the latter so fascinating: repeating always the same supposedly «universal» worldviews or ideas eventually becomes boring and predictable, and prevents us from recognizing the individuality and creativity of so many figures in the esoteric field.

4) A fourth problem is the fact that scholars continue to be uncertain about *what the field of «esotericism» is really all about*. Some scholars keep thinking in terms of the old Warburg models of a Hermetic tradition and its later continuations; others continue to think in the explicitly religionist and esoteric terms of «inner traditions»; yet others are using Faivre's model of esotericism as a «form of thought», although they are usually unaware of its true backgrounds in a specific form of Christian theosophy, illuminism, and *Naturphilosophie* (see above); others again are trying to get away from these older models, for example by embracing a «discursive» approach as proposed by Kocku von Stuckrad (but note that in his latest work, von Stuckrad rejects the notion of “Western esotericism” as a historical concept [Stuckrad 2010; Hanegraaff 2012: 362–367]); others again (like myself) are critical about the non-historical implications of an exclusive focus on discourse and want to use it only within the broader perspective of intellectual history; yet others are mostly concerned with «the occult» in modern and popular culture, and care little or nothing about a larger historical approach. The list could perhaps be expanded further. Of course we do not all need to agree about everything; but we do need to develop an acceptable, updated *scholarly* research paradigm that is no longer based on the old models or on esoteric or religionist commitments, and that is capable of integrating the results of cutting-edge research within the various disciplines involved in our field.

5) This brings me to a fifth problem. There is a rather strong tendency of thinking that our field is concerned with the history of «esoteric traditions» as a more or less autonomous phenomenon, at the expense of recognizing its radical *interdisciplinarity*. The realization has not sufficiently sunk in that Western esotericism does not fit comfortably within *any* of the established academic disciplines but participates in *all* of them: religion, philosophy, science, literature, art, music, or the social

sciences. If we think of «the Western esoteric traditions» as an autonomous domain of its own (see, for example, [Goodrick Clarke 2008]), then we are paying our field a bad service, for scholars in the various existing disciplines of the humanities will then have little or no reason to take an interest in it. Instead, we should make clear that, for example, art historians have reason to see esotericism as an underestimated dimension of their *own* field. The same goes for historians of philosophy, historians of science, and so on. To illustrate this with one more example from that last domain: if we insist on the old idea that alchemy is an «esoteric discipline», and keep suggesting (against the evidence) that its practitioners are therefore not concerned with scientific research, the result is that we will never be taken seriously by historians of science. Instead, if we see *all* the dimensions of alchemy (from strict science to religious interpretations) as pertaining to our field of research, then the doors are open for fruitful collaboration. In short: we must not remain a field enclosed in its own circle, with its own set of favourite authors and so on, for that kind of provincialism does not fit our topic of research. We must throw open the doors wide open to all the disciplines in the humanities and even the social sciences.

6) Finally, the level of *scholarly quality* in our field simply needs to be improved. We must become more critical about maintaining standards of academic excellence, and our ambition should be to operate at the highest level of critical research and intellectual debate. It is not enough to be satisfied about the fact that we have attained some level of acceptance in the academic world: as far as I am concerned, our goal should be to play a major role in it, for as I suggested earlier (and explain at length in my most recent book [Hanegraaff 2012]) our field does have the potential of revolutionizing the way in which the humanities are looking at the history of Western culture. So far, this potential has hardly been recognized yet; and it will never come to fruition unless we place our standards of scholarship as high as possible and insist on letting our voice heard not just in our «own» circles but in other academic contexts as well.

Western Esotericism 3.0

For all these reasons, then, I believe it is time for a serious upgrade to «Western esotericism 3.0». This new and improved program is not available on the market yet, but I would suggest it should have at least the following characteristics:

1) It must be up-to-date and in line with advanced contemporary research in the various relevant domains.

2) Its agenda must not be esoteric (or krypto-esoteric) but scholarly throughout.

3) It must have a solid grounding in detailed historiography.

4) It must be based on a reasonably clear consensus about what «Western esotericism» is all about.

5) It must be open and interdisciplinary.

6) It must be of high quality.

Now, most of these recommendations are fairly straightforward and should in fact hardly be controversial: I do not expect that anyone will disagree about the principle that our work should be scholarly, of high quality, open and interdisciplinary, up-to-date, and historically grounded. I do hope, however, to have convinced the reader that «Western esotericism 2.0» still falls short of the ideal in all these respects and we will need to work hard to improve it. The only point that will certainly remain controversial for quite some time is the fourth one: what do we really mean by «Western esotericism?» In conclusion I would therefore like to zoom in on that point a bit further.

Many definitions of «Western esotericism» have been proposed over the last twenty years, and we could no doubt go on inventing new ones. But a solution to our problem will not be found there: it will only lead to more disagreement. It is more fruitful, in my opinion, to ask ourselves what is essentially at stake in these discussions of definition. To make clear what I mean by this, I would like to make a brief excursion to modern theories of cognition. The anthropologist Tanya Luhmann has pointed out, in an entirely different context, that in everyday practice we do not in fact categorize things by means of formal lists of criteria («X is esoteric because it fits characteristics a, b, & c»). Rather, we usually categorize things by comparing them to «prototypes». A prototype is a cluster of characteristics that is seen as constituting a «good example» of a class. Here is how Luhmann explains it: «When you use prototypes in your thinking, you ask whether the item in question resembles the best example of that class, not whether it meets specified rules or criteria of that category. Is an ostrich a bird or a grazing animal? A prototype user asks himself whether the ostrich is more like a sparrow or more like a cow, relying both on what he can see and on an array of background theory and assumptions. <...> When you look at a piece of furniture to decide whether it is a table or a chair, you do not list the rules of membership in the “table” and “chair” categories in your mind. That takes time. It also often does not work, since many category members do not have all the apparent criteria of the class (a bird that cannot fly, like the penguin, is still a bird). <...> You do not ask yourself whether this chair meets the

criteria for chairship. You look at it, and you know it's a chair [Luhrmann 2000: 41].

Scholars have provided various sets of criteria to define what should or should not fall in the category of «Western esotericism», but the truth is that they have almost always been reasoning by prototype. That is to say, scholars already have some «best examples» in mind of the class that they see as Western esotericism, and then proceed to compare specific historical phenomena to that model. Depending on the model they have in mind, some historical currents may be included by some scholars but excluded by others; and this, I suggest, accounts for most of the confusion about the field and its boundaries. The three most common models underlying current concepts of Western esotericism seem to be the following: 1) an «enchanted» pre-Enlightenment worldview with ancient roots but flourishing in the early modern period, 2) a wide array of «occult» currents, ideas, and organizations that emerged after the Enlightenment as alternatives to traditional religion and rational science, 3) a universal, «inner» spiritual dimension of religion as such.

Let us look at these three models a bit more closely. If we consider the famous criteria proposed by Antoine Faivre, it is evident that they read like a definition of «enchantment», set against the «disenchanted» worldviews associated with post-cartesian, post-newtonian and positivist science. Faivre's notion of «correspondences» is clearly conceived as an alternative to linear or instrumental causality. «Living nature» stands against mechanistic and materialist worldviews. The notion of «imagination / mediations» implies a multi-leveled Platonic cosmology as opposed to a cosmos reducible to only matter in motion; and it suggests not only that there are various «subtle» levels of reality intermediary between the poles of pure spirit and pure matter, but also that we may gain access to them by means of the imagination (which is therefore an organ of knowledge and not just a fabricator of illusions, as held by Enlightenment rationalism). «Transmutation», finally, refers to a spiritual process of regeneration or rebirth by means of which fallen man and nature may be reunited with their divine origin and source. In short: «esotericism» according to Faivre's definition looks like a radical alternative to the disenchanted worldviews that came to dominate Western culture in the wake of the scientific revolution, the Enlightenment, and positivist science. For Faivre himself, the prototypes *par excellence* of Western esotericism belong to a movement in early modern culture – roughly from Paracelsus in the sixteenth century to the Romantic era – that is known as Christian theosophy and *Naturphilosophie*. Accordingly, whether any other religious or intellectual

currents should be seen as forms of esotericism depends, for him, on how close they are to this «best example» of the class. In practice, this means that the early modern period looms largest in Faivre's work, as the golden age when Western esotericism flourished like never before or after. Ancient and medieval sources are acknowledged as a necessary background, rather than as manifestations of esotericism in their own right. And most importantly, it remains somewhat questionable – and never fully explained in Faivre's oeuvre – whether the many esoteric or occultist currents that developed through the nineteenth and twentieth centuries up to the present are still close enough to the theosophical/naturphilosophical prototype to qualify as «esotericism» at all. In terms of Luhrmann's analogy: if esotericism is an enchanted sparrow that clearly differs from a disenchanting cow, then these post-Enlightenment forms of esotericism seem to be hybrid animals that might easily be dismissed as pseudo-esotericisms. In a very different way, Frances Yates' concept of «The Hermetic Tradition» is based on a prototype of «early modern enchantment» as well. An important implication in both cases is that, by definition, esotericism *must* be at odds with the secular world and can never be seen as an integral dimension of modern culture and society. Even if it manages to survive under post-Enlightenment conditions, it can only do so as an anti-modernist «counterculture» engaged in an ultimately hopeless «flight from reason».

The second prototype is entirely different. It might be argued (and has in fact been argued) that esotericism, or the occult, did not emerge as a social phenomenon in its own right before the eighteenth or even the nineteenth century. Before that time it had been just an intellectual tradition manifested in learned and popular writings; but only now did it take the form of actual organizations and social networks that began to compete with the established churches on a pluralistic «market» of religion. From such a perspective, precisely the occult in modern and contemporary culture is the central core phenomenon, the prototypical «best example» of what Western esotericism is all about. Earlier periods may be interesting as historical background, but are far from crucial or central; and the criteria for defining and demarcating the field must be derived from its post-Enlightenment manifestations. One example of this approach can be found in the work of Christopher Partridge, and his notion of «occulture» [Partridge 2004]. In sharp contrast with the first prototype, this second one is grounded firmly in modern culture and contemporary society. «Esotericism» or the occult does not function here as an object of nostalgia for a lost or forgotten enchanted worldview, but is a dimension of the here and now, with implications for the future.

Finally, according to a third influential model of Western esotericism the term stands for «inner» traditions concerned with a universal spiritual dimension of reality, as opposed to the merely external («exoteric») religious institutions and dogmatic systems of established religions. This prototype stays closest to the original meaning of the adjective «esoteric» in late antiquity, when it referred to secret teachings reserved for a spiritual elite, such as the Pythagorean brotherhoods or some mystery cults. Exoteric teachings, according to this model, are meant for the uneducated masses that can be kept satisfied with mere ritual observance and dogmatic belief systems. Underneath the surface of conventional religion, however, there are deeper spiritual truths that are known only to initiates into the true mysteries of religion and philosophy. According to this prototype, the true esoteric spirituality must ultimately be one, independent of social, historical, or cultural circumstances. Regardless of the tradition in which one has been raised, those who refuse to be satisfied with outward appearances and limited dogmatic systems will always be able to find access to the universal truth about the nature of the world, of divinity, and of human destiny to which all the great mystics and spiritual teachers have been referring. Here, we are evidently dealing with a religionist approach on esoteric foundations. The problem is that, because of its consistent emphasis on universality and continuity, it is difficult or even impossible to combine with strict historical research, as I have already tried to explain above. Whether we like it or not, scholarly research is «exoteric» by definition and can only study what is empirically available to observers regardless of their personal convictions: it has no instruments for gaining direct access to the true and absolute nature of reality that is claimed to exist according to this model, and it has no methodologies for either verifying or falsifying the claim that such a reality exists in the first place. The Absolute or the Divine is simply not a possible object of research.

In my opinion, *none* of these three prototypes should be the normative basis of discussion in the study of esotericism. It is more useful, and more in accord with the evidence, to look at Western esotericism as a radically pluralistic field of currents, ideas, and practices that can be studied from late antiquity to the present day, *without* seeking to privilege any historical period or any particular worldview as «more truly esoteric» (that is, closer to some prototype of esotericism) than any other. From that perspective, and contrary to all the approaches I have just been discussing, *there is no such thing as a «best example» of esotericism*. But obviously, such an agenda begs the question of definition and

demarcation, for it still assumes that the field *as a whole* can be set apart as somehow different from other fields of inquiry.

On what basis, then, can we do so? In my recent book «Esotericism and the Academy: Rejected Knowledge in Western Culture», I argue that the field that we nowadays call Western esotericism can be described as the chief casualty of academic specialization after the eighteenth century. What initially sets it apart is its modern status as «rejected knowledge»: it contains precisely everything that was consigned to the dustbin of history by Enlightenment ideologues and their intellectual heirs up to the present, because it was considered incompatible with normative concepts of religion, rationality, and science. Imagined as the radical counterpart of everything that educated people are expected to take seriously, the consensus among mainstream intellectuals after the eighteenth century was that this domain should better be avoided and ignored in academic discourse instead of being dignified by detailed study and analysis of its ideas and their development. This process of exclusion and neglect did not just happen overnight: on the contrary, it was the final outcome of a long history of apologetic and polemical battles and negotiations, beginning in late antiquity, about the question of which worldviews and approaches to knowledge should be considered acceptable and which ones should be rejected. It is through these debates that the emerging religious and intellectual elites were defining their own identity by means of creating an «other» that represented the opposite of how they saw themselves.

If «Western esotericism» is the academy's dustbin of rejected knowledge, this does not imply that it is just a random collection of discarded materials without any further connection. On the contrary, a broad consensus had emerged around the eighteenth century about the chief characteristics of the rejected domain. Although one can never take polemical narratives at face value – almost by definition, they exaggerate and simplify for maximum effect – those characteristics do in fact correspond to recognizable worldviews and approaches to knowledge that have played an important although always controversial role in the history of Western culture. In order to study them (and explain to others what it is we are studying), we do *not* need a substantive definition about what esotericism is «really» all about: it is sufficient to make clear which currents, ideas, or personalities have come to be placed in the dustbin of history. Our task, as I see it, is to overturn that dustbin, studying its contents, and restore them to their legitimate place in history and society. If we go about this task seriously and ambitiously enough, and refuse to be satisfied with anything less than excellent quality, our field of research

may end up revolutionizing the way we understand Western culture as a whole¹.

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¹ Some passages in this article have been taken from *Hanegraaff W. J.* Western Esotericism: A Guide for the Perplexed. London: Bloomsbury, 2013.

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